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IMMEDIATE EFFECT OF SURYANAMASKAR ON BLOOD LACTATEMr. Prasenjit Kapas¹ & Dr. Sridip Chatterjee²¹Ph.d Scholar (JRF), Department of Physical Education, Jadavpur University²Assistant Professor, Department of Physical Education, Jadavpur University**Abstract**

Introduction: Surya namaskar (SN), or Salutation to the sun, is an important hatha yogic practice which has been handed down from the sages of vedic time. Surya Namsakar is almost a complete sadhana (practice) in itself, containing asana, pranayama and meditational techniques within the main structure of the practice. **Objective of the Study:** The main objective of the present study was to see the immediate effect of Suryanamaskar on blood lactate. **Methods:** The study was conducted in the Department of Physical Education at Jadavpur University, Kolkata. To meet the purpose of the study 15 male students from Bachelor of Physical Education course with mean age 23.8 ± 1.89 yrs were acted as subject in the present study. Subjects were performed 8 rounds (12 steps) of Suryanamaskar in the early morning in light stomach. Blood sample was collected before commencement of SN and immediately after 8 rounds of SN practice. Lactate Analyzer used for measuring the amount of lactate concentration in the blood. To analyse the data mean and standard deviation was used as descriptive statistics and 't' test was employed as inferential statistics for the comparison of pre and post exercise lactate level in the blood. **Results:** Before exercise blood lactate level was recorded as 10.86 ± 1.41 mg/dl and immediately after 8 rounds of suryanamaskar practice it reached at 16.35 ± 1.31 mg/dl. 8 rounds of Suryanamaskar practice produce a significant ($p < .05$) increase of blood lactate level in pre to post exercise session. **Conclusion:** On the basis of the present study we may conclude that suryanamaskar is a moderate physical activity, could be recommended for the maintenance of general cardiovascular health-fitness status of the individual.

Keywords: Suryanamaskar, exercise, blood lactate

Introduction

Blood lactate is the by-product of glucose utilization by muscle cells. Blood lactate is continuously produced by skeletal muscle at rest and at all levels of exercise (1). Generally it forms when the body breaks down carbohydrates to use for energy and when oxygen levels are low. Blood lactate levels represent the balance between lactate production and lactate metabolism.

Lactate is an important biomarker, as disruption to the pH in the blood is a possible sign that instrumental work for athletes is taking place. An increase of lactate in the blood could signal an increase of endorphins and the occurrence of other physiological responses, and it's a great workhorse biomarker for sport scientists and coaches alike.

During exercise blood lactate tests can be a useful indicator of what is happening in some parts of energy systems in our body. Blood lactate tests work by measuring the amount of lactic acid present in the blood. Lactic acid is always produced in some quantity, along with another intermediate by-product called pyruvate, in the long sequence of reactions that take place in the breakdown of glucose during exercise. At moderate intensities, lactic acid usually breaks down and re-enters the energy pathways to release energy in the presence of oxygen.

Suryanamaskar is an effective way of loosening up, stretching, messaging and toning all the joints, muscles and internal organs of the body (2). It also helps to improve blood circulation throughout the whole body. Suryanamaskar is a mild to moderate exercise which may produce moderate work load on heart. Suryanamaskar practice improves general health and fitness (3). Patima et al. (2008) in a study concluded that regular Suryanamaskar practice improves cardiopulmonary efficiency in healthy adolescents and is beneficial exercise for both males and females (4). In a previous study it was reported that Suryanamaskar keeps one within his lactate or anaerobic threshold and exerts a moderate stress on cardio-respiratory system (5).

Suryanamaskar is a useful cardiovascular exercise, which could affect the blood lactate level in muscles cell. There are reports regarding effect of SN on cardio respiratory or cardiovascular system (4,5,6), but there is no report available on blood lactate aspects of SN. Keeping the above in mind this study was planned to investigate the immediate effect of suryanamaskar on blood lactate.

Materials and Methods

Study location

The present study was carried out in the Department of Physical Education, Jadavpur University, Kolkata, West Bengal, India.

Subjects

The sample of this research consisted of 15 male B.P.Ed students. The subjects had experience to participating in yogic practice. They were healthy residential male participants. Subjects' age range was between 20-25 years, belonging to almost the same socio economical background. The participants with injury, ill health were excluded from the study. The subjects were informed about the procedure and possible risk of the research. The informed consent was obtained from all the participants.

Study Design

The purposive sampling method was adopted for this present study.

Table-1: Experimental session for measuring blood lactate:

Description	Resting for 10 minutes	Measurement of BL Before Exercise(pre-test)	Measurement of BL after assigned 8 round SN practice(post-test)
Position of the subject	Supine Lying position	Chair sitting Position	Chair sitting Position

BL- Blood Lactate, SN- Suryanamaskar

Procedure

This is a single group pre-post experimental study. Subject were performed Suryanamaskar for 8 rounds in the early morning with light stomach. Suryanamaskar consisted of a series of 12 steps yogic postures. Blood lactate was measured before and after completion of Suryanamaskar practice.

Administration of Test

After 12 hour fasting blood was taken from the subject in early morning. Before exercise blood was taken from the subject in chair sitting position. Then subject was performed 8 rounds of Suryanamaskar. After exercise again blood was collect from the subject. Then lactate concentration in the blood was measured by the spectrometry method.

Fig no-1; Blood collection from the subject

Result

The demographic details of all participants are presented in table no.2

Table 2: Demographic detailed of the participants

Total participants	Age(year)	Weight(kg)	Height(cm)	BMI(kg/mt ²)
15	23.8 ± 1.89	62.06 ± 4.31	167.9 ± 5.51	21.98 ± 0.95

Blood lactate results are presented below in the table no-3

Table 3: Results of pre & post test of blood lactate

	Pre-Lactate Level(mg/dl)	Post-Lactate Level(mg/dl)	<i>t-value</i>	table value
Mean	10.86	16.35	14.66	2.14 df = 14
Standard Error	0.36	0.34		
Standard Deviation	1.41	1.31		
Minimum	8.9	14.1		
Maximum	13.1	18.2		
Count	15	15		

Fig no-1: Mean difference of blood lactate before & after Suryanamaskar practice

Table No-3 reveals that before suryanamaskar practice blood lactate level was recorded as 10.86 ± 1.41(mg/dl) and after 8 rounds suryanamaskar practice it reached at 16.35 ± 1.31(mg/dl). The changes from pre-test to post test was significant at 0.05 level.

Discussion

The main finding of this experiment is that Suryanamaskar practice produce a significant increase in blood lactate level of the participant. Suryanamaskar is a moderate type of yogic exercise helps to provide a better overall musculo-skeletal and cardiovascular fitness. A significant difference of blood lactate observed between pre-post exercise session of the Suryanamaskar practice. All the changes of blood lactate were significant at 0.05 levels.

Blood lactate level not only express the level of fatigue but it also a good marker of exercise intensity. In a study De paoli et all. (2007) reported that blood lactate actually serves as a performance-enhancing chemical, rather than being the cause of muscle fatigue (7). In the present study before suryanamaskar practice blood lactate level was recorded as 10.86 ± 1.41 (mg/dl) and after 8 rounds suryanamaskar practice it reached at 16.35 ± 1.31 (mg/dl), which confirms that suryanamaskar is a moderate yogic exercise which produce physical stress on the human body.

No direct review study was found which interpret the present study in broad way. On the basis of the present experimental study it can be interpreted that Suryanamaskar is a moderate physical activity can be recommended for the maintenance of general cardiovascular health fitness status of the individual.

Conclusion

From this scientific study we may conclude that Suryanamaskar is moderate exercise intervention can be recommended for develop good and healthy general fitness status of the individual.

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